

Steric Enhancement of Resonance : Kinetics of the Reaction of Acetophenones with Pyridine and Iodine

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The kinetics of the reaction of a number of mono-, di- and tri-substituted acetophenones with pyridine and iodine at 30° have been investigated. Evidence for steric enhancement of resonance is obtained from the rate constants of 3-substituted-4-methoxyacetophenones and 3-substituted-4-methylthioacetophenones. The calculated rate constants of 4-methoxy-3-methylacetophenones, 3-methyl-4-methylthioacetophenone, 3-halogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones and 3-halogeno-4-methylthioacetophenones are considerably higher than the observed rate constants indicating that the 3-substituent enhances the resonance interaction between the methoxy and carbonyl groups and also between methylthio and carbonyl groups. The expected steric inhibition of resonance is observed in 3,5-dihalogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones, 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyacetophenone and 3,5-dimethyl-4-methylthioacetophenone. The above phenomenon "steric enhancement of resonance" has also been analysed in terms of Hammett's sigma constants. The effective sigma value ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the resonance interaction energies for the mono- and di-substituted compounds have been calculated and presented.

AFTER the discovery of the phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance by Baliah and Uma¹ while studying the electric dipole moments of substituted anisoles, numerous work has been done by several authors^{2-4,6,7} by kinetic methods to substantiate this view. The dissociation constant data⁸ of some substituted benzoic acids and the diamagnetic susceptibilities of some substituted benzene derivatives obtained by Jeyanthi⁹ lend further support. Recently the present authors¹⁰ have studied the kinetics of oxidation of acetophenones by chloramine-T and the kinetics of the bromination of acetophenones both in acidic and basic media, adducing additional evidence. The present investigation which deals with the study of the kinetics of substituted acetophenones with pyridine and iodine, provides further support for this concept.

Experimental

Materials and Methods : The substituted acetophenones were prepared by standard methods described in the literature¹¹⁻²⁰. Liquid ketones were purified by distillation and the solid ketones by recrystallization to constant melting points. The b.p./m.p. were in agreement with literature values. Pyridine was purified²¹ by drying it over solid sodium hydroxide and then treating with the mixture of anhydrous zinc chloride and ethyl alcohol.

The kinetics of all the ketones were determined by the conductivity method²². It was found that a plot of 1/R against time gave a straight line. Extrapolation of the straight line portion of the curves to the equilibrium resistance gave the hypothetical time necessary to complete the reaction.

Results and Discussion

It has been shown by King²³ that ketones react with iodine in the presence of excess pyridine to give high yields of β -ketoalkyl pyridinium iodides. The reaction has been extended to include a variety of ketones and heterocyclic amines²⁴. In the reaction of acetophenones with iodine, the ketone and pyridine were present in sufficiently large excess so that their concentrations remained essentially constant during kinetic studies. Since the reaction is of first order with respect to the ketone and zero order with respect to iodine, the pseudo zero order rate constant k_0 was calculated first. Finally, the pseudo first order rate constant, k_1 , is obtained by dividing k_0 by the concentration of the ketone. The mechanism²⁵ formulated is :

Of these reactions Step 1 is the slowest and is rate-determining.

For structural correlation i.e., comparison of reactivity, the pseudo first order rate constants were taken into account. The first order rate constants k_1 along with pseudo zero order constants k_0 for mono-substituted acetophenones are given in Table 1 which shows the order of reactivity as,

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE MONO-SUBSTITUTED ACETOPHENONES

Substituent	$k_0 \times 10^6$ mol litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^4$ min ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^4$ min ⁻¹	van der Waal's radii (A) of 3-substituents	k_{cal}/k_{ob}
None	16.67	5.71	—	—	—
<i>m</i> -methyl-	9.41	3.72	—	—	—
<i>m</i> -Fluoro-	17.55	8.09	—	—	—
<i>m</i> -Chloro-	31.29	10.03	—	—	—
<i>m</i> -Bromo-	37.55	12.95	—	—	—
<i>m</i> -Iodo-	37.89	14.63	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-	11.32	2.36	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Methylthio-	3.12	4.22	—	—	—

Rate Constants for Di-Substituted Acetophenones and Relationship between Relative Enhancement of Resonance and van der Waal's Radii

	(observed)	(calculated)		
4-Methoxy-3-methyl-	5.66	1.55	—	1.20
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy-	5.55	3.47	1.35	1.17
3-Chloro-4-methoxy-	6.81	3.87	1.80	1.30
3-Bromo-4-methoxy-	6.84	4.47	1.95	1.45
3-Iodo-4-methoxy-	5.97	4.52	2.15	1.62
3-Methyl-4-methylthio-	14.15	2.55	—	1.08
3-Chloro-4-methylthio-	4.91	4.77	1.80	1.55
3-Bromo-4-methylthio-	4.76	5.29	1.95	1.81

Rate Constants for Tri-Substituted Acetophenones

3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxy-	8.71	3.10	—	—
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy-	32.61	12.88	—	—
3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxy-	8.77	12.35	—	—
3,5-Diiodo-4-methoxy-	3.00	4.62	—	—
3,5-Dimethyl-4-methylthio-	9.31	4.95	—	—

$m-I > m-Br > m-Cl > m-F > H > p-SCH_3 > m-CH_3 > p-OCH_3$

A quantitative analysis has been made using Hammett equation. A fairly linear plot (Fig. 1) between $\log k/k_0$ and Hammett's sigma constants is obtained. The positive ρ value (+0.97) obtained in this case is the measure of the susceptibility of the reaction. The correlation coefficient r is 0.95 (S.D. = 0.085).

p-Methylthioacetophenone reacts faster than *p*-methoxyacetophenone showing less electron releasing tendency. This is because of the difference in the primary quantum number between the lone-pair electrons (3p) of sulphur and the aromatic π electrons (2p), the mesomeric electron release from the substituent to the ring is less important for sulphur than for oxygen.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k/k_0$ versus Hammett's sigma constants (1) *p*-Methoxy- (2) *m*-Methyl- (3) *p*-Methylthio- (4) Unsubstituted- (5) *m*-Fluoro- (6) *m*-Chloro- (7) *m*-Iodo- and (8) *m*-Bromo-.

The rate constants of di-substituted acetophenones are given in Table 1. A comparison of the calculated rate constants for all the di-substituted acetophenones on the basis of additivity principle⁵ with the observed rate constants indicates

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUENT CONSTANTS FOR MULTIPLE SUBSTITUENTS

Substituent	$\Sigma\sigma$	σ_{found}	$(\sigma_{found} - \Sigma\sigma)$	$\Delta\Delta F$ k cal/mole
4-Methoxy-3-methyl-	-0.397	-0.582	-0.245	-0.3295
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy-	0.069	-0.228	-0.292	-0.3927
3-Chloro-4-methoxy-	0.105	-0.174	-0.279	-0.3752
3-Bromo-4-methoxy-	0.123	-0.110	-0.233	-0.3133
3-Iodo-4-methoxy-	0.084	0.021	-0.063	-0.0847
3-Methyl-4-methylthio-	-0.116	-0.361	-0.245	-0.3295
3-Chloro-4-methylthio-	0.326	-0.081	-0.407	-0.5474
3-Bromo-4-methylthio-	0.344	-0.034	-0.378	-0.5084

that the substituents at 3 position sterically enhances the electron releasing mesomeric interaction of $-OCH_3$ and $-SCH_3$ groups with the aromatic ring. As the bulkiness of the groups increases the relative enhancement of resonance also increases. In all the di-substituted acetophenones the k_{cal}/k_{obs} value is greater than unity as expected. The relative ratios are given in Table 1 along with the van der Waals radii of the corresponding 3-substituents.

In view of the Jaffee's^{2,3} conclusion, the effect of multiple substitution on the reactivity of side chain can be expressed by the Hammett equation in the form

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \Sigma\sigma$$

The substituent constants for multiple substituents are calculated and compared with the sum of the individual substituent constants ($\Sigma\sigma$) and are given in Table 2. The negative sign of the (σ found $-\Sigma\sigma$) values indicates that the electron release is greater in these compounds than expected. In a reaction series where a substituent enters into mesomeric interaction with the reaction centre, a multiplicity of (exalted) σ values is observed. This holds for +M as well as for -M substituents. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the resonance interaction energy²⁰ ($\Delta\Delta F$) were calculated and presented in Tables 2 and 3. It is evident from the data in the Tables 2 and 3 that the effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) differ considerably from σ values. The enhanced values indicate important and substantial increase of resonance interaction between the substituent and the reaction centre in the transition state. The result is quite compatible with the mechanism as represented in the reaction scheme.

TABLE 3—EFFECTIVE σ VALUES AND RESONANCE INTERACTION ENERGY OF MONO-SUBSTITUTED ACETOPHENONES

Substituent	σ	$\bar{\sigma}$	$(\bar{\sigma} - \sigma)$	$\Delta\Delta F$ k cal/mole
<i>m</i> -Methyl-	-0.069	-0.1914	-0.1224	-0.1646
<i>m</i> -Fluoro-	0.337	0.1550	-0.1819	-0.2446
<i>m</i> -Chloro-	0.873	0.2517	-0.1212	-0.1630
<i>m</i> -Bromo-	0.391	0.8662	-0.0248	-0.0933
<i>m</i> -Iodo-	0.852	0.4210	0.0690	0.0928
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-	-0.268	-0.3090	-0.0410	-0.0551
<i>p</i> -Methylthio-	-0.047	-0.1356	-0.0886	-0.1191

The rate constants for tri-substituted acetophenones are given in Table 1. It is significant to note that a single substituent ortho to the $-\text{OCH}_3$ group or $-\text{SCH}_3$ group enhances the resonance interaction of both $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{SCH}_3$ groups with the para $-\text{COCH}_3$ substituent. The expected steric inhibition of resonance is however, observed for 3,5-dihalogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones, 3,5-dimethyl-4-methoxyacetophenone and 3,5-dimethyl-4-methylthioacetophenone. The low value of the rate constant for 3,5-diiodo-4-methoxyacetophenone is explained as follows. As the bulkiness of the substituent alone is taken into consideration, 3,5-diiodo-4-methoxyacetophenone should have a higher value as chloro- and bromo-compounds do. The striking behaviour in the case of iodine is due to the fact that in addition to +M and -I effect,

-M effect plays a predominant role thereby making the order reversed.

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